

Order in publication	Firstname	Middle name	Surname	Conceptualization [1]	Data curation [2]	Formal analysis [3]	Funding acquisition [4]	Investigation [5]	Methodology [6]	Project administration [7]	Resources [8]	Software [9]	Supervision [10]	Validation [11]	Visualization [12]	Writing - original draft [13]	Writing - review & editing [14]	Email address	Primary affiliation	Secondary affiliation	Funding	ORCID ID	Corresponding author?
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2	Christophe		Dony	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cdony@uliege.be	University of Liège	NA	NA	0000-0001-1111-1111	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

- [1] Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.
- [2] Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later re-use.
- [3] Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data.
- [4] Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication.
- [5] Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.
- [6] Development or design of methodology; creation of models.
- [7] Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution.
- [8] Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools.
- [9] Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.
- [10] Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team.
- [11] Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.
- [12] Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.
- [13] Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).
- [14] Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.